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IN SILICO EVALUATION OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGICAL POTENTIAL AGAINST *DAPHNIA MAGNA* OF SUCCINIMIDE DERIVATIVES FROM FOUR HOMOLOGOUS SERIES

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Abstract

Ecological monitoring analysis confirm that organisms in the environment are chronically exposed to complex multi-component pharmaceutical mixtures. Thus, the ecotoxicological evaluation of new pharmaceuticals and their negatively impact on ecosystems and aquatic life become integral step in the process of drug design and development. One of the most common model organisms for evaluation of freshwater toxicity of chemicals is *Daphnia magna*. Both experimental and computational methods are being developed for prediction of the ecotoxicological potential of new structures. In this paper ADMETlab 3.0 online program was employed for evaluating the concentration that kills 50% of *Daphnia magna* after 48h (LC₅₀DM) for 45 succinimide derivatives. The obtained results indicated that the observed compounds have less toxic effect in comparison to registered ethosuximide and similar toxic effect as phensuximide. The highest LC₅₀DM or the least toxic effect was recorded for most lipophilic compounds of the series F with statistically significant higher LC₅₀DM in comparison to series C, D and E respectively. In addition their toxic effect was positively associated with their polarity (TPSA, p=0.001), aquatic solubility (logS, p<0.001) and flexibility (Fsp3, p<0.001), respectively and negative associated with the Van der Waals volume (V, p<0.001) and lipophilicity (both logP and logD, p<0.001 for both), respectively.

Introduction

Ecotoxicological assessment has a crucial role in evaluating the environmental risks of pharmaceutical substances. Regulatory agencies worldwide require ecotoxicity testing as an integral component of the environmental risk assessment process, emphasizing proactive strategies to mitigate the impact of pharmaceutical contaminants. Green ecotoxicology introduces sustainable methodologies to evaluate the effects of compounds on ecosystems, reducing environmental harm while providing accurate information on chemical ecological hazards. This approach integrates advanced predictive tools and environmentally friendly techniques to facilitate the development of safer substances with minimized ecological effects [1]. *Daphnia magna* (water flea) is one of the most commonly used model organisms to assess freshwater toxicity of wide range of pharmaceuticals. The flexibility of *Daphnia magna* to cope with environmental stressors, its sensitive behavioural and physiological responses serve as reliable biomarkers for assessing the effects of diverse chemicals. Additionally, the use of *Daphnia* in toxicity testing aligns with the principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) in animal research, making them an ideal model organism for developing and evaluating methods to assess emerging contaminants and environmental concerns [2, 3]. In

parallel with traditional ecotoxicity assessments, there is a growing shift toward the integration of *in vitro* testing and computational modelling approaches, reflecting a broader trend toward alternative, non-animal methods in environmental risk assessment.

Succinimide moiety has been recognized for various pharmacological effects [4, 5]. The design of new structures and development of potential pharmaceuticals with succinimide core undergo the testing for its ecotoxicological risk. The aim of this research was to assess *in silico* the toxicological effects of 45 compounds (Table 1) from four series (C, D, E and F) on *Daphnia magna* and to evaluate the influence of their physico-chemical features on these values.

Experimental

In this paper in ADMETlab 3.0 online program (<https://admetlab3.scbdd.com/>) was used for evaluating the ecotoxicological potential of 45 succinimide derivatives (Table 1). For each compound their two-dimensional structures were obtained by the ChemDraw Professional as Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System, SMILES. This form was used for evaluation of their properties. Various features of the analysed compounds were evaluated including the polarity expressed as total polar surface area (TPSA), solubility given as logS, lipophilicity calculated as partition coefficients (logP and logD), their size measured as volume (V) and their flexibility expressed as Fsp3 were determined. The ecotoxicological potential of each compound was evaluated as the concentration that kills 50% of *Daphnia magna* after 48h and presented as LC₅₀DM. The values were given in $-\log_{10}[(\text{mg/L})/(1000 \cdot \text{MW})]$. All statistical analysis were conducted using OriginPro 8 and $p < 0.01$ was considered as statistically significant.

Results and discussion

The 48h-LC₅₀ for *Daphnia magna* based on the ADMETlab 3.0 online program were determined for all the observed compounds and are presented in Figure 1. Both series C and series D had statistically significant lower LC₅₀DM in comparison to series E and F respectively ($p < 0.01$), while series E also had statistically significant lower LC₅₀DM when compared to series F ($p < 0.01$). There were no statistically significant differences in the values of LC₅₀DM between series C and D. As model compounds phensuximide and ethosuximide, registered antiepileptic drugs were also tested. LC₅₀DM for phensuximide was 4.231 while for ethosuximide was 2.551. Based on the predicted values, all of the compounds analysed had higher LC₅₀DM (3.470-6.038) in comparison to ethosuximide, which means they have lower ecotoxicological potential in freshwater when compared to this medicine. All compounds of series F (LC₅₀DM interval 5.181-6.038) as well as some compounds of series C, D and E had also higher LC₅₀DM when compared to phensuximide as well. The lethal potential of the analysed compounds towards *Daphnia magna* according to the *in silico* screening results makes them less or equally hazardous in freshwater as medicines with succinimide moiety already present on the market.

The increment of LC₅₀DM was positively associated with the size of the analysed molecules calculated as Van der Waals volume (V) in statistically significant manner ($r^2 = 0.551$, $p = 3.193 \times 10^{-9}$). These results are in accordance with literature data about the influence of the size on the toxicological effects of the molecules, classifying small molecules as more hazardous [6]. In addition, the higher the lipophilicity (logP and logD, respectively) of the analysed compounds was, the higher were LC₅₀DM values. Namely, a statistically significant relationship was obtained between logP and LC₅₀DM ($r^2 = 0.857$, $p = 9.451 \times 10^{-12}$, Figure 2a) and logD and LC₅₀DM ($r^2 = 0.870$, $p = 8.913 \times 10^{-12}$), respectively for all 45 succinimides investigated in this study. It is generally accepted that the higher lipophilicity is associated to enhanced permeability and higher toxicity of the molecules [7]. However, experimental data often

contradict these claims. Our data are in concordance with the findings of Tafreshi et al. as more targeted alpha-particle therapy with higher lipophilicity exhibited less toxic effect in animal models [8].

Table 1. Structures of the compounds analysed

Series C			Series E		
Compound	-R ₁	-R ₂	Compound	-R ₁	-R ₂
C1	-H	-H	E1	-COOH	-H
C2	-CH ₃	-H	E2	-Cl	-H
C3	-OCH ₃	-H	E3	-Cl	-H
C4	-OH	-H	E4	-H	-Br
C5	-COOH	-H	E5	-H	-Cl
C6	-H	-COCH ₃	E6	-CH ₃	-H
C7	-COCH ₃	-H	E7	-OH	-H
C8	-NO ₂	-H	E8	-H	-H
C9	-Cl	-H	E9	-OCH ₃	-H
C10	-Br	-H	E10	-F	-H
C11	-I	-H	E11	-CN	-H
C12	-H	-Cl			
C13	-H	-Br			
Series D			Series F		
Compound	-R ₁	-R ₂	Compound	-R ₁	-R ₂
D1	-H	-H	F1	-CH ₃	-H
D2	-OH	-H	F2	-OCH ₃	-H
D3	-OCH ₃	-H	F3	-H	-H
D4	-COOH	-H	F4	-NO ₂	-H
D5	-CN	-H	F5	-F	-H
D6	-CH ₃	-H	F6	-Cl	-H
D7	-NO ₂	-H	F7	-Br	-H
D8	-Cl	-H	F8	-H	-Cl
D9	-Br	-H	F9	-H	-Br
D10	-H	-Cl	F10	-H	-I
D11	-H	-Br			

Figure 1. 48h-LC₅₀DM values of the analysed series of succinimide derivatives

The reduced toxicological potential of the more lipophilic compounds may be attributed to their restricted solubility, as higher lipophilicity is followed by poor aqueous solubility [9]. Accordingly, there was negative association between the solubility displayed as logS and the LC₅₀DM of the observed succinimides ($r^2=0.884$, $p=3.481 \times 10^{-12}$, Figure 2b). Moreover, the negative association was established between Fsp3 which presented the ratio of the number of sp³ hybridized carbons and the total carbon count and LC₅₀DM ($r^2=0.418$ $p=9.657 \times 10^{-7}$). This inverse relation between Fsp3 and LC₅₀DM which follows the negative association between logS and LC₅₀DM is expected as Fsp3 correlates with the aqueous solubility of the molecules.

Figure 2. Statistically significant association of LC₅₀DM with a) logP and b) logS, respectively for the observed succinimide derivatives

Finally, the polarity (TPSA) was also negatively associated with the LC₅₀DM ($r^2=0.210$, $p=0.001$). Our results are supported by the previous finding that indicate that more polar

compounds exhibit higher toxicity especially in specific environmental samples such as freshwater [10].

Conclusion

Ecotoxicological assessment of newly synthesized compounds which are drug candidates becomes mandatory step in the drug development process. Forty-five succinimide derivatives based on the *in silico* evaluation had lower or similar toxicity potential against *Daphnia magna* in comparison to the drugs with succinimide core registered on the market. The most lipophilic structures of the series F had the least pronounced toxic potential in comparison to the compounds of the series C, D and E. The toxic potential towards *Daphnia magna* according to the *in silico* evaluation for the observed compounds is governed by their polarity, solubility and flexibility in a positive manner. On contrary, the Van der Waals volume and the lipophilicity of the compounds seem to decrease the toxic potential towards *Daphnia magna*.

References

- [1] S.S. Panda, Green Anal. Chem. 11 (2024) 100162.
- [2] A. Tkaczyk, A. Bownik, J. Dudka, K. Kowal, B. Ślaska, Sci. Total Environ. 763 (2021) 143038.
- [3] K. Reilly, L.A. Ellis, H.H. Davoudi, S. Supian, M.T. Maia, G.H. Silva, Z. Guo, D.S.T. Martinez, I. Lynch, Front. Toxicol. 5 (2023) 1178482.
- [4] S. Kovačević, M.K. Banjac, N. Milošević, J. Čurčić, D. Marjanović, N. Todorović, J. Krmar, S. Podunavac-Kuzmanović, N. Banjac, G. Ušćumlić, J. Chromatogr A. 1628 (2020) 461439.
- [5] D. Pinter, N. Milošević, M. Milanović, D. Vidović, J. Kvrđić, V. Kojić, D. Jakimov, J. Drljača Lero, N. Milić, B. Božić, N. Banjac, J. Biochem. Mol. Toxicol. 39 (2025) e70313.
- [6] R.E. Hewitt, H.F. Chappell, J.J. Powell, Curr. Opin. Toxicol. 19 (2020) 93-98.
- [7] M.R. Naylor, A.M. Ly, M.J. Handford, D.P. Ramos, C.R. Pye, A. Furukawa, V.G. Klein, R.P. Noland, Q. Edmondson, A.C. Turmon, W.M. Hewitt, J. Schwochert, C.E. Townsend, C.N. Kelly, M.J. Blanco, R.S. Lokey, J. Med. Chem. 61 (2018) 11169-11182.
- [8] N.K. Tafreshi, H. Kil, D. N. Pandya, C.J. Tichacek, M.L. Doligalski, M.M. Budzevich, N.C. Delva, M.L. Langsen, J.A. Vallas, D.C. Boulware, R.W. Engelman, K.L. Gage, E.G. Moros, T.J. Wadas, M.L. McLaughlin, D.L. Morse, ACS Pharmacol. Transl. Sci. 4 (2021) 953-965.
- [9] A. Sharapova, M. Ol'khovich, S. Blokhina, G.L. Perlovich, Molecules. 27 (2022) 6504.
- [10] Y.H. Zhao, X.J. Zhang, Y. Wen, F.T. Sun, Z. Guo, W.C. Qin, H.W. Qin, J.L. Xu, L.X. Sheng, M.H. Abraham, Chemosphere. 79 (2010) 72-77.